

CHALLENGES DETERRING EFFICIENT AND EFFECTIVE LAND SERVICE DELIVERY IN LAND MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT BUREAU OF ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA

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Abstract

Institutional capacity is the primary key factor to ensure efficient and effective land service delivery. Despite several endeavours made by successive Ethiopian governments, most institutions are still lacking the required capacity to deliver responsive, transparent, competitive, and quality services to their respective clients. The article, hence, is aimed at establishing the capacity associated challenges deterring the efficient and effective delivery of land services in Ethiopia specifically emphasizing on Land Management and Development Bureau of Addis Ababa. To achieve the objective, descriptive research and explanatory design and mixed approach were applied. The data were collected from the main office and five sub-city administration offices using Key Informant Interviews, Focus Group Discussions, and questionnaire. The gathered data were analysed qualitatively and quantitatively using thematic and SPSS Version 23 software. The study result indicates that though there are individual capacity building attempts, it is proven that there is inadequate motivation, staff support, and supervision. Even though, proper land service delivery requires the existence of far-sighted, forward-looking and strategic leadership, the research findings established the existence of serious problem to this end. Furthermore, adequate collaboration and cooperation among different units is also missing. The performance management system is also deficient. Based on the research findings, the authors concluded that the organization is not sufficiently capacitated to deliver efficient, effective, and responsive land services to their clients. To mitigate the challenges, building leadership capacity and commitment, providing demand-driven and need-based training, creating a collaborative work environment and team spirit are suggested as pertinent intervention measures.

Keywords: *Institutions, institutional capacity, service delivery, land service, Ethiopia*

1 BACKGROUND AND JUSTIFICATION

An emphasis on institutional building and development has increased significantly in most developing countries. It is highly important to have strong institutions, particularly in the public sector, as dysfunctional and ineffective public institutions and weak governance are increasingly seen to be at the heart of the development challenge. Misguided resource allocation, excessive government intervention, coupled with arbitrariness and corruption have deterred investments and slowed growth and poverty-reduction efforts in numerous settings (WB, 2000).

Institutions are backbones to any political and economic endeavours as they determine the behaviours and outcomes of organizations (Luiz, 2009). To play this key role, institutions need to be ready in terms of human resources, technological capacity and utilization, leadership capacity and commitment, and physical resources among others so as to effectively support efficient and effective service delivery. Institutional readiness for reforms is a comprehensive attitude influenced simultaneously by the nature of the reform, the reform process, the organization's context, and the attributes of individuals. Changes to the technological, economic, socio-cultural, and political environments in which organizations operate are also increasingly becoming important for organizational survival (Amis & Aïssaoui, 2013). With that said, it

remains something of a truism to note that organizational change and reform are inherently difficult to accomplish with studies of private and public sector organizations suggesting that about 70% of change programs fail to be implemented as planned, if at all (Craine, 2007; Ford & Ford, 2009; Clegg & Walsh, 2004). It is argued that the inability to implement reform programs as planned are attributed to problems associated with institutional capacity.

In Ethiopia, previous successive regimes have been weakening existing institutions resulting in successive political leaderships instigating missing layers of institutional improvements in the country (Asfaw, 2019; Admassie, 2006; Mengesha & Common, 2006). Due to the factors emanating from the very nature of the regime and among other things, the high regard given to political loyalty in assigning civil service posts and the level of political interference affecting standard operating procedures, the institutions repeatedly failed to deliver the intended service to the public (Mengesha & Common, 2006). Broich (2017) argued that institutional developments are undermined and get less attention in resource allocations like budget, skill, knowledge, technology, and entrepreneurship as it takes a long time to produce meaningful results (Sasaoka, 2005; Israel, 1987; Asfaw, 2019). The inability to passably include indigenous institutions into formal ones is also another gap in institutional development in Ethiopia as most of the values and contents of the institutions have been copied from different imported political ideologies (Asefa, 2003; Admassie, 2006).

The Ethiopian public sector has undergone a massive process of restructuring in the last three decades. The justifications for the reforms were to make it more responsive to the desires of the citizens' through improving the levels of accountability, transparency, efficiency, and effectiveness. They were also aimed at increasing the participation of the citizens by adopting customer-focused practices. Despite such a massive effort exerted by the government, most empirical studies conclude that the reform results were not impressive. The authors argue that the institutional capacity deficit of public sector organizations contributed to the problem.

The existence or the lack of efficient institutions explain why some political and economic reforms are successful and become developed and others continue to be trapped in poverty (Asefa, 2003; Muhula, 2019). In line with this, Ethiopian high officials recently uttered the word "institutions" and "institutionalization" as a driver of sustainable development. The Prime Minister has also promised to work on forming and strengthening institutions. To this end, many political and economic reforms were made. Besides the many economic and political reforms, many scholars argue that those reforms are less institutionalized, not consultative and deliberative which adversely affects its irreversibility and sustainability as the existing political culture is under debate and where the rules and norms for the peaceful contestation of power is relatively undeveloped (Verjee, 2019). Even though the governments of Ethiopia have been implementing a number of reforms, utmost they are not institutionalized and claimed to be strongly politicized. With this reality, the article is aimed at identifying structural and organizational challenges affecting the efficient and effective delivery of land services taking Land Management and Development Bureau of Addis Ababa as a case organization.

2 BRIEF OVERVIEW ON THE TRENDS OF INSTITUTIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN ETHIOPIA

To have a comprehensive understanding of the institutional capacity associated challenges facing the land sector in Ethiopia, the authors believe that it's pertinent to briefly present the trends of institutional development in the country's contemporary history. As already established by various scholars, institutional development in Ethiopia lacks continuity and have a slow growth (Kenea, Teshome, & Yemane, 2020; Apaza, 2022; Emiru, 2022; Desalegn & Solomon, 2021; Amente, Terefe, & Kecho, 2022) which is primarily manifested by the quality of services delivery within the public institutions. Partly due to lack continuity, and also lack of proper record keeping and destruction of any existing record, there isn't ample literature about institutions and institutional development in Ethiopia during successive governments. Most other developing Sub-Saharan African countries also share the same experience as empirical evidences are scanty. Apparently, institutional capacity development efforts are resource consuming and takes a long-time to produce any meaningful outcomes (Sasaoka, 2005). This section of the article, therefore, is aimed at establishing the nature of institutional capacity development during the three successive governments with special attention to areas where lessons can be drawn.

During his reign, Emperor Haile-Selassie undertook a series of institutionalization and restructuring measures, mainly after 1941, in the hope of bringing about an efficient and effective civil service governed

by specified rules and procedures of a uniform nature (Mengesha & Common, 2006). Though Ethiopia had a very good late-start advantage at building its institutions, the pace of growth was not as impressive as expected. The World Bank characterizes the imperial regime approaches and strategies of government structure by the dominance of adamant centralization of power, inequitable regional development, and little participation of citizens in various affairs (World Bank, 2013). Due to the very nature of the Imperial Regime, in recruiting and assigning civil service posts, high regard was given to political loyalty (Mengesha & Common, 2006). As a result, there was high degree of political interference that adversely affected standard operational procedure and the efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery. Despite the monarchical nature of the state and absence of democratic governance, Emperor Haile-Selassie recorded key achievements, domestically and globally, that the present and future generation of Ethiopians can take lessons from (Asefa, 2003).

The Derg Regime came to power in 1974 by abolishing the monarchical regime of Haile-Selassie. Derg began its rule by entirely abolishing institutions established and developed by the Emperor and replaced them with the Soviet Union version of totalitarian system of governance (Asefa, 2003). The regime's nationalization initiative led to expansion of the new public sector in the country (Mengesha & Common, 2006). The system established by the regime encouraged individuals and organizations to behave in a destructive manner rather than behaving constructively (Asefa, 2003). Consequently, Ethiopia was at the lowest threshold of development in terms of several development parameters (World Bank, 2013).

Broich (2017) argued both the Imperial and Derg regimes lacked accountable and transparent institutions even for proper delivery of aid at a time when the country was in need of immediate food assistance. As a result, delivery of foreign aid among the population was based primarily on political favoritism and nepotism. After the downfall of the Derg regime, the transitional government issued a constitution with the fundamental aim of restoring the capacity of the state and shaping its structures and functions and thereby to ensure stability and promote economic growth (World Bank, 2013). The transitional government acknowledged the existence of serious institutional constraints in terms of delivery of efficient, effective, responsive, and transparent services to the citizens (Mengesha & Common, 2006).

In addition to recognizing the presence of institutional constraints, the EPRDF (Ethiopian Peoples' Revolutionary Democratic Front) government undertook several institutional reforms to build the capacity of public sector organizations with the long-term vision of poverty alleviation, creating a conducive environment for investment and economic growth, and democratization (Mengesha & Common, 2006). CIDA added that during the EPRDF regime, Ethiopia is uniquely positioned in terms of building the capacity of public institutions established Ministry of Capacity Building and Development (CIDA, 2010). Though successive governments of the country gave attention to develop institutional capacity with different degrees, there are still multi-faceted institutional problems deterring effective and efficient service delivery.

3 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURES

The apprehension regarding institutional situations becomes significant in developing countries. This is due to the fact that the formal institutional system is not well developed and the vast majority of societies do not have practice in experiencing the market economy. This argument is supported by various empirical findings. Yukhanaev and his associates, for instance, found out that insufficient market freedom, high levels of corruption, excessive and dysfunctional bureaucratic regulation are hindering the development of ready and capable institutions (Yukhanaev et al., 2015). Furthermore, the absence of an appropriate and suitable institutional framework coupled with a lack of proper implementation affects the effectiveness of organizations (Hoxha, 2009).

Changes to the technological, economic, socio-cultural, and political environments in which organizations operate are increasingly becoming an important characteristic of organizational survival (Amis & Aïssaoui, 2013). Undeniably, a failure to capture the cultural, political, and social issues is inescapable. It has been a point of ongoing concern for many (Pascale, Milleman, & Gioja, 1997; Meyer & Rowan, 1977; Amis & Aïssaoui, 2013; Weiner, Amick, & Lee, 2009).

The primary reason for the inefficient and ineffective functioning of institutions is the problem associated with human capital (DFID, 2018). Human capital is one of the most important factors that determine the effective and successful functioning of any organization. Training, equipment, and staff are elements of organizational capacity, but institutional effectiveness also depends on how organizations and

individuals interact with institutions - on 'political processes in which rules are respected, avoided or negotiated' (DFID, 2017, p. 12). Besides, as the public sector institutions are influenced by social and political norms, capacities need to be assessed in civil society and the private sector as well as the state. The creation of an enabling environment for organizational and institutional development requires looking beyond state structures to society, the economy and ideology (Berman, 2013).

Leadership is also the determinant factor that affects the capacity of any organization. This is mainly because weak leadership capacity contributes to the weak performance of an organization. Hence, differences in institutional capacity could explain the differences in outcome i.e. the extent and magnitude to which organizations deliver expected service to their respective clients (Ghanem, 2017).

Lack of political commitment is a common explanation for PSIR (Public Sector Institutional Reform) failures (Anuradha & Becky, 2015). It can be linked to factors such as reform fatigue, patronage networks, and a lack of financial incentives (Scott, 2011) as well as aims such as staying in power and satisfying elite supporters. In such settings, increasing political participation could simply enhance the power of local elites (Brinkerhoff & Goldsmith, 2004; Unsworth, 2010; DFID, 2017).

Different empirical studies illustrate that political commitment predominantly on the part of higher leadership opens space for institutional capacity development (Unsworth, 2010; Fritz et al., 2012). According to Derrick Brinkerhoff, political commitment and ownership can be measured in terms of the impetus for change is external or internal, whether domestic actors have been the drivers in assessing policy options, outcomes and benefits, social commitment and allocation of resources, sustainability of effort and commitment (Brinkerhoff, 2017).

Monitoring and evaluation provides stakeholders with regular information on progress related to targets and outcomes (Ernest et al., 2019). Proper coordination, monitoring and evaluation systems are integral pillars of any organizations. This is because sound coordination, monitoring and evaluation enhance the contribution of the organization by establishing a clear link between past, present and future initiatives and developments (UNDP, 2009). It also helps organizations to extract relevant information from the past and ongoing activities that can be used for future planning. Nevertheless, ample empirical studies show the prevalence of poor coordination, monitoring and evaluation systems (Osifo, 2013; Vanagas & Stankevic, 2014). Paul Kariuki and Purshottama Reddy in their empirical work established that monitoring and evaluation capacity is low in most of the studied organizations in South Africa (Kariuki & Reddy, 2017). The situation in other developing countries is not peculiar.

In a note stressed on scrutinizing the trends and results of institutional capacity building in Africa focusing on Ethiopia and Mozambique, Carmen Apaza established that incompetent and poorly trained and educated manpower, insufficient remuneration which is resulting in high rate of turnover in some sectors such as health, weak and ineffective accountability devices, deep-rooted corruption, inadequate finance and wastage of the existing meager financial resource are identified as challenges deterring the effective functioning of public institutions in Ethiopia (Apaza, 2022). The scholar also established that public service organizations, particularly at the Woreda level, uses around 90% of their allocated budget for effecting salaries and operational costs, instead of directing them towards institutional capacity development. It's factual that without developing institutional capacity, the goal of ensuring sustainable development and bringing millions of Ethiopians out of poverty line is unthinkable.

From the reviewed literatures, it can be concluded that despite consecutive efforts exerted by successive Ethiopian governments to ensure institutional development through capacity building in the country, there still exist challenges. Sasaoka in his assessment of institutions building for poverty reduction in Ethiopia, Tanzania and Kenya concluded that there are many problems in the area of institution building such as budget allocation, poverty monitoring, transfer of capitation grants, and accountability building in domestic society (Sasaoka, 2005). FAO validated the limited capacity in terms of budget, and skilled and committed human power has negatively affected the effective functioning of the gender apparatuses in federal and regional Women and Child Affairs Offices (FAO, 2019). This among other illustrates that the country is still under multi-faceted institutional problems and the government need to continue working towards improving the situation.

4 METHODS AND MATERIALS

In a scientific research, the researchers can choose an approach that suits to the research based on the nature of data required, objectives sought to be achieved, and the problem to be studied. Accordingly, the

authors adopted a mixed research approach so as to collect, analyze, and interpret both qualitative and quantitative data with the purpose of gaining better and comprehensive understanding of the research problem. Mixed approach is vital to triangulate, cross-validate, and dig the research problem intimately (Sale, Lohfeld, & Brazil, 2002). It also generates deeper and broader insights, and facilitates a far better understanding of the connection between variables of interest.

Descriptive and explanatory research designs were used in amalgamation. Descriptive design enabled the authors to be flexible by using multiple sources of knowledge involving literature review, key informant interview, focus group discussions, and survey to use both quantitative and qualitative analysis. On the other hand, explanatory design was used to measure the magnitude of the predictor (institutional capacity) variables has on the resultant (service delivery efficiency and effectiveness). It focuses on an analysis of situations or specific problems to explain the nature and patterns of relationship between variables of interest (Sauders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009).

The subject of the study constitutes all the sub-cities Land Management and Development Bureau of Addis Ababa employees. Among the population under the study, five-sub-city Land Management and Development were selected based on the geographical location. Bole from the east, Kolfe-Keranio from west, Gulele from north, Akaki-Kality from south, and Kirkos from the central part of the city administration were selected on the ground of representativeness and to have a comprehensive and exhaustive understanding of the issue at the city administration level. Besides, the deliberate selection of the aforementioned sub-cities is on the assumption that their characteristics is representative of the remaining ones and thus provide accurate and in-depth conceptualization of the research variables.

In order to triangulate the data collected from employees, sixteen (16) interviews were conducted with randomly selected clients of the organization, until the point of data saturation, specifically empathizing on the challenges they are encountered during the service delivery and their understanding of the institutional capacity of the organization. Convenient sampling technique was used in selecting the interviewees. On the other hand, professional public servants working at the bureau and sub-city level were selected purposely due to the assumption that they have better theoretical and practical knowledge and information concerning the issue under the study. Reports associated with institutional capacity and service delivery of the bureaus and selected sub-cities were also analyzed.

5 EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE ON THE CHALLENGES DETERRING EFFICIENT AND EFFECTIVE LAND SERVICE DELIVERY

Human resource is one of the most important factors that determine the effective and successful delivery of any services. This is mainly because the success or failure of an organization fundamentally depends on the success or failure of its human resource. According to Joel Rodriguez and Kelly Walters, employees are the backbone of the organization (Rodriguez & Walters, 2017; Trubetskaya & Mullers, 2021; Goswami, Gopal, Hamida, & Kumar, 2023). They found accomplishments or issues experienced by the organization are contingent on the performance of its employees. The capacity of organizations' human resources can be measured in terms of their respective skills and knowledge among other things (Yusoff et al., 2013). The data obtained indicated that 79.7% of employees believe that they have the required knowledge and skill to properly undertake their duties. Nonetheless, some key informant interviewees and FGD discussants argued thought there is sufficient human resources in terms of number, there are problems associated with their efficiency. They expressed that the existing human resource are *"not all rounded and equipped with the required skill and knowledge"*. Comprehensively, there exist problems related to equipping employees with the necessary skill and knowledge. Thus, the skills and knowledge of human resources have to be built continuously to bridge the existing gap.

Training is critical to improving the existing skill gap for employees mainly due to the constantly evolving nature of works. It also ensures the competitiveness of an organization. Different empirical studies show training increases the productivity and performance of an organization (Habib & Wazir, 2012; Daniel, 2018; Long et al., 2016). Further, it improves the skill and knowledge in their job and thereby builds their confidence (Daniel, 2018). This will, in turn, improve the performance of an organization and contributes to its effectiveness (Ogbu & Idowu, 2017; Samwel, 2018). As a result, employee training is something unavoidable in the organization and should not be overlooked or undermined (Samwel, 2018). This is due

to the fact well trained, competent and experienced employees meet the goals and objectives of their organizations.

The research result illustrates that, though the organization is providing limited trainings opportunities, the trainings were not immune from challenges. According to one FGD participant:

“Despite the capacity building effort, it is not without limitations. The first problem is the employees’ attitude towards the training. Most of them don’t pay attention to training contents, they rather focus on financial benefits and refreshment. Secondly, training institution/trainers don’t start from the gap identified i.e. training contents, materials and training methods don’t fit to the context and gap identified. Thirdly, there is a problem of repeating the same training several times. Furthermore, the training programs are also more of theoretical and doesn’t expose the trainee with their desired work-related and practical skill demanded”.

It is clear that the provision of training to employees presents an opportunity to expand the horizon of their skill and knowledge. It is also empirically proved that employees who receive the necessary training are able to better perform their job in comparison with the ones who do not have access to training. The investment in training contributes towards improving employee satisfaction and morale and thereby creates a supportive workplace. Further, employees who feel appreciated and challenged through training opportunities may feel more satisfied with their jobs. Studies also indicate that access to training reduces employee turnover in organizations. In spite of such advantages of providing training, the surveyed employees established the serious gap to this end.

Support and supervision is an essential aspect of human resource management. Adeyemo Moridiyat stated that support and supervision have always played an important role in effective and successful performance (Moridiyat, 2017). He noted support and supervision are required to translate plans into actions and necessary to ensure that the subordinates are working in accordance with the plan and policies of the organization. More importantly, support and supervision should emphasize on problem-solving and involves two-way communication between the supervisor and supervisee (Ian & Lisa, 2018).

Support and supervision is primarily aimed at enhancing or improving the performance of individuals in an organization. It also provides an opportunity to employees to identify any skill gap and developmental needs aimed at mitigating the gap and ensuring organizational employees are competent enough to undertake their duty effectively. The survey data illustrates only 16.4% of the employees believed in the presence of ‘very high’ support and supervision from their supervisors. FGD participants expressed even whenever there are follow-up and support, the feedback provided in the process cannot be considered by the organizations for further improvements.

The low level of support and supervision given to employees by the supervisor largely attributed to low leadership commitment. The research also established the existence of a leadership capacity deficit. This was supported by the statement from one of the key informants who stated *“I believe there is a capacity gap both on the leadership and implementers. The leaders in particular are not resilient and exhibit a tendency to be challenged by daily events. There is also a gap of knowledge, skill and attitude on the part of leadership”.* The focus group discussant also elaborated that majority of the leadership are not willing and ready to engage in capacity building programs, particularly those designed at the organizational levels.

Technology has become part of society’s everyday functioning (Wihan, Eileen, & Jan, 2016). It is changing rapidly and providing widespread mobility and connectivity to employees which make the utilization and familiarity with information and communication technology a necessity. Recently, the public sector is required to be as competitive as the private sector particularly in delivering the necessary services to their clients. This requires the usage of information and communication technology.

It’s established that the appropriate utilization of innovative technologies among employees allow them to work faster, communicate easier and more rapidly, makes work easier, and improves the quality of work (Wihan, Eileen, & Jan, 2016). Effectively using the technology further enable employees to have continuous access to work information, systems, and documents even when not at work, this creates a mobile workforce (Anyaegbunam, 2017). Further, it also contributes to making the work more flexible with time, allows multi-tasking, and makes individuals more flexible in their activities (Neetu, 2018).

The study result illustrates a significant portions of the survey participants rated the adoption of appropriate innovative approaches in the management and operations of their respective organizations between ‘very low’ and ‘moderate’. Though the application of innovation contributes significantly to the effectiveness of reform in many public organizations, the survey result shows a gap in the studied

organization in terms of using this important tool towards the realization of their vision. However, one of the key informant's interviewees from the quality improvement department stated, *"we started using online technology to enable investors' access our services being wherever they are. We believe this contributes to attracting further investment"*. Another FGD participant reported that *"the expansion of COVID-19 pandemic has forced many employees to work from home using different online platforms that have increased the usage of technological infrastructure"*. This in general shows though there is a gap in providing and using innovative technological infrastructure, key informants, and focus group discussants indicated the presence of improvement in using innovative technologies.

An empirical study conducted by John Ross and his associates in their study aimed at examining the contribution of technology to educational reform and effective service delivery found that access to technology contributes to the implementation of education reform and proper service delivery (Ross et al., 2002). They also identified the existence of computers promoted equity of access to all forms and strands of education but this did not necessarily ensure that all students had access to the higher results. Likewise, adopting innovative approaches in the management and operations of organizational functions enhances the accessibility of the service. Yet, it doesn't guarantee the efficient and effective delivery of land services.

The survey also established the existence of adequate technological infrastructure for proper service delivery. Barbara Means and Kerry Olson found the existence of positive and a significant association between the level and effectiveness of service delivery and the availability of technological resources (Means & Olson, 1995). This indicates that the more technological resources are available, the better the probability for effective service delivery. Cognizant of this fact, findings from this study revealed the problem associated with proving some technological resources. Nevertheless, data obtained from key informants show the existence of an effort to establish a database that easily connects different units of the organization and with other organizations.

As put by Elvis Selase and Bienmali Kombate, an organizational structure is among the pillars of proper service delivery in public sector organizations (Selase & Kombate, 2018). They empirically established that public sector organizations perform better when structures and good policy mechanisms are in place. Further, they proven efficient and effective service delivery is more driven by structure, leadership capacity and effective communication networks than rules, regulations, procedures, and incentive packages. In this regard, the researcher studied if the structure of the study organization is enabling, appropriate, and suitable for proper and responsive service delivery to the clients. Accordingly, the obtained results show that 53.3% of the survey participants expressed their agreement to the existence of appropriate and enabling organizational structure. One KII interviewee indicated that the organization is currently revisiting its structure to address the concerns of the customers and ultimately deliver transparent, efficient and effective land services.

Organization need the allocation of relevant and sufficient resources including but not limited to financial and human resources to realize its mission. This is mainly because it is hardly possible to undertake any activity in their absence. These resources require careful utilization, particularly in public sector organizations. In spite of this fact, the data obtained through the survey illustrated that 64.9% of the respondents do not believe that the government is allocating the required and sufficient finance and human resource needed for proper service delivery. Many key informants and FGD participants confirm the same as there is a gap in terms of mobilizing and allocating sufficient budget and human resources. Additionally, one key informant expressed that *"the existing human resources in the organization are not exhaustively using their capabilities for efficient and effective service delivery"*. This added to the other factors, hinder the successful service delivery in the organization.

Delivering efficient and effective services requires extra amount of skill, knowledge, cooperation and motivation. It has a little chance of succeeding if those who are responsible for managing and implementing, do not have the appropriate skill, knowledge, motivation, and incentives (Paul, 2010). Beyond their role in discharging their assigned duties and responsibilities, civil servants' capacity building and motivation are now consistently acknowledged as a critical factor in determining performance in the public sector.

The success of an organization depends on the quality of human resources it possesses. In addition to recruiting individuals with the required competence, organizations have the challenge of assigning the right person in the right position. Rosman Yusoff and his colleagues argued, based on their empirical findings, putting the right person in the right place at the right time increases employees productivity and motivation

and thereby contributes towards the realization of organizational goals and objectives (Yusoff et al., 2013). Empirical research conducted in Pakistan further illustrated that assigning the right person to the right position led 79% of the projects to success (Naqvi, Kashif, & Safwan, 2011). It is also regarded as central in leading organizational growth and progression. Nonetheless, this process is not an easy task.

Opinion is divided among employees, key informants, customers, and FGD participants on the issue of assigning the right personnel at the right position. About 32.9% of the employees expressed that although there are appropriate positions in their respective organizations, employees are not assigned to it. Yet, 31.6% of the survey participant employees in contrary expressed all employees are assigned to positions they are qualified for. One key informant argued the application of Job Evaluation and Grading (JEG) helped the process of assigning the right personnel in the right position. Assigning individuals to the right position plays an important role in ensuring efficient and effective service delivery. To this end, as specified by one FGD participant, "there is a need to avoid rampant networking". Thus, establishing a merit-based system where individuals compete only on the basis of their performance is an appropriate measure.

Table 1: Challenges deterring the efficient and effective land service delivery

Variables	VLSC	LSC	ASC	SC	VSC	Total	Weight	RII = W/(5*Total)	Rank
Scale Values	1	2	3	4	5				
Absence of relevant system that can handle complaints in the organization	18	45	137	83	55	338	1126	0.666	4 th
Poor monitoring and evaluation system	16	68	113	95	46	338	1101	0.651	7 th
Inadequate capacity of the leadership to effectively oversee what is really happening in the organization	24	65	92	100	57	338	1115	0.660	5 th
Absence of helpful mechanisms for complaint submission for customers	18	110	88	84	38	338	1028	0.608	16 th
Inappropriate organizational structure	13	91	98	88	48	338	1081	0.640	10 th
Absence of clear rules and regulations	30	80	142	44	42	338	1002	0.593	17 th
Absence of clear land policies	27	76	108	83	44	338	1055	0.624	14 th
Absence of effective performance management system where performance is periodically evaluated and action is taken accordingly	15	48	123	107	45	338	1133	0.670	3 rd
Lack of effective and timely communication among different stakeholders	19	73	127	79	40	338	1062	0.628	13 th
Uncommitted human resource	15	59	140	80	44	338	1093	0.647	8 th
Lack of adequate and necessary working equipment's and materials including convenient offices	8	94	117	92	27	338	1050	0.621	15 th
Presence of management and leaders that can't understand effective human resource development practices including employees' motivation and reward systems as well as	4	50	109	107	68	338	1199	0.709	1 st

effective system of performance management									
Lack of sufficient financial resource that can ensure proper operation of land services	33	62	113	57	67	332	1059	0.638	11 th
Lack required skill and knowledge on the part of employees	25	38	137	93	45	338	1109	0.656	6 th
Corruption and malpractices	11	83	117	77	50	338	1086	0.643	9 th
Absence cooperation and collaboration among different offices	10	59	115	86	68	338	1157	0.685	2 nd
Inability to provide adequate and necessary working equipment's and materials	11	89	113	84	41	338	1069	0.633	12 th

Source: Own Survey Result, 2023

One of the fundamental objective of the research was identifying the challenges deterring the efficient and effective service delivery in land sector. To this end, employees were requested to orderly rate the challenges identified through review of related theoretical and empirical literatures. Then, using Relative Importance Index (RII) their respective rank was determined. Accordingly, as depicted in table 1 above, employees rated 'presence of management and leaders that can't understand effective human resource development practices including employees' motivation and reward systems as well as effective system of performance management' as a primary factor blocking the delivery of efficient and effective land services. It is proven that leadership within an organization plays a paramount role in ensuring efficient and effective land service delivery, among others, by guiding the efforts of team members, inspiring and motivating employees, exerting a positive influence, setting standards, and fostering a positive and collaborative work culture. Hence, the delivery of proper land services to the clients requires the existence of far-sighted, forward-looking and strategic leadership, Nonetheless, the existing reality on the ground is typically different. The possible attributor factor to this problem might be the frequent reshuffling and change of leadership which is emerging as a core challenge affecting the proper service delivery. FGD discussants argued most leadership appointments are not based on adequate and thorough research or back-check.

Absence cooperation and collaboration among different units, absence of effective performance management system where performance is periodically evaluated and appropriate action is taken accordingly, absence of relevant system that can handle complaints in the organization, and inadequate capacity of the leadership to effectively oversee what is really happening in the organization are ranked as the next serious challenges in respective orders. It's repetitively reported by different concerned government stakeholder that the land service is one of the highly corrupted compared with other services. The surveyed employees, however, ranked 'corruption and malpractices' in 9th order. The employees also pointed that the clients are expecting from the management to solve the accumulated problems within unreasonable time schedule. This in turn is putting unnecessary pressure on the leadership.

6 CONCLUSION AND POLICY DIRECTION

Efficient and effective land service delivery requires human, financial, material, and technological capabilities. Among these, human capacity plays a lion's share in determining the successful service delivery. In order to extract this capability from employees, proper staffing, or the assignment of the person to the right position is highly required. In this regard, the study concludes that "rampant networking" coupled with organizational failure and the absence of appropriate structure hinders the proper utilization of existing capacity. It was also found that most employees have the required knowledge and skill for discharging their duties and responsibilities even though there is doubt on their efficiency.

Though different efforts are continuously exerted by organization, it is concluded from the study findings there are gaps in providing and using innovative technological infrastructures. It was found there were requirements to use technological infrastructures though the absence of appropriate allocation of financial resources and continuous technological capacity building was identified as a challenge. Proper service delivery highly demands continuous follow-up, supervision, motivation, and capacity building efforts. The research revealed the existence of a gap in providing timely follow-up and supervision. The motivation of the employees was found to be low as

the research findings revealed. It was also found that, despite the critical relevance of training, limited trainings being provided are not need-based and demand-driven. Overall, the level of institutional of institutional capacity required to deliver efficient and effective land services was found to be inadequate. To mitigate the identified challenges, the following policy options, among others, are required:

- To successfully leverage the technological capacity, allocating sufficient budget for innovative technological infrastructure is important. To this end, the Bureau has to show political commitment in proving funds required for the efficient and effective service delivery. Alternatively, the Bureau can also collaborate with donors without compromising the policy directions of the government. Whenever the required budget is obtained and allocated, there is a need to design an appropriate and innovative controlling mechanism whereby misappropriate utilization of financial resources can be minimized.

- Ensuring structural harmonization and alignment among work units is suggested as an option to enable effective structural functioning and avoid functional overlaps. This can be done through cooperation and jointly working with each other's.

- Frequent reshuffling and change of leadership are found to be a challenge effective service delivery. Hence, to mitigate this problem, leadership appointments have to be based on sufficient and thorough back-check to avoid frequent reshuffling.

- To improve the quality of service delivery, the Bureau need to emphasize on follow-up, supervision, and capacity building programs. For this purpose, they need to strengthen feedback platforms. On the other hand, they have to provide continuous and need-based and demand-driven practical training on the service delivery.

- It was found that lack of commitment and support from management is the major challenge deterring effective service delivery. To improve the management level of commitment and support to proper service delivery, there is a need to create strong accountability framework and sense of ownership.

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